

FIC Fighters

FIC-Fighters Deliverable 6.2

Communication Toolkit

Summary:

The Communication Toolkit encompasses the project logo and different materials allowing project partners to promote the FIC-Fighters project in a consistent way. This document summarises the available resources and indicates where project partners and the public can access them.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 6.2, the Communication Toolkit, includes the project logo, a suite of promotional materials, and various templates designed to enable project partners to promote the FIC-Fighters project in a cohesive and professional manner. These resources ensure consistency in messaging and visual identity, adhering to the communication guidelines established in Deliverable 6.1.

The toolkit provides a comprehensive set of tools to support outreach activities, ranging from event promotion to stakeholder engagement. By standardising the project's branding and messaging, the materials aim to enhance recognition and strengthen the overall impact of the FIC-Fighters project.

This document offers an overview of the available resources, as of January 2025, and provides clear instructions on how project partners, as well as the general public, can access and utilise them. The toolkit represents an ongoing effort to ensure that the project's communication strategy remains effective, adaptable, and aligned with its goals.

2 FIC-Fighters logo

2.1 About the logo

The FIC-Fighters logo (Figure 1) was designed with the view to depict the circular economy process of transforming phosphogypsum waste into sustainable raw materials used in various industries. The vibrant blue and green colour gradient shall convey a positive image, representing social and environmental progress and innovation. The overall style is intended to be clean and modern. The icon in the middle of the logo represents a thriving and sustainable city and the circle reminds the circular economy concept.

Figure 1: FIC-Fighters logo.

The project logo must be placed on all published materials. This includes not only promotional materials, but also deliverables, event announcements, factsheets, infographics, presentations or agendas. The logo is available in different file formats in the project's internal repository and also via the website: <https://fic-fighters.eu/media-kit/>

These different logo versions are illustrated and described in detail in the project's stylebook, which forms Annex 1 of Deliverable 6.1. The stylebook furthermore provides detailed information on the project's colour palette, the fonts to be used and different templates made available to partners.

2.2 INFORMATION ON EU FUNDING

According to the Grant Agreement¹, the following rules apply while communicating about FIC-Fighters:

“17.2 Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 2: EU emblems.

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

¹ See ARTICLE 17 — COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY, pp. 38-40.

(...)

17.5 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 28).

Such breaches may also lead to other measures described in Chapter 5.”

3 FIC-Fighters leaflet and brochure

Project partners have access to two handy resources introducing the project at a glance: a compact leaflet in business card-sized format (Figure 3) and a detailed trifold brochure (Figure 4). These materials can be distributed either electronically or as printed hard copies at events.

Given growing environmental concerns, many organisations prefer to minimise the printing of hard copies. The business card-sized leaflet provides an eco-friendly option, as its small size and lightweight design make it a practical choice for sharing essential information with minimal environmental impact. The leaflet includes a QR code which leads the visitor to the project website for more information.

The trifold brochure, on the other hand, offers a more comprehensive overview of the project, detailing its objectives and expected outcomes. It serves as a valuable complement to the leaflet and is particularly suited for stakeholders seeking a deeper understanding of the project’s scope and vision.

Both resources are designed to support effective communication and engagement with a wide range of audiences, ensuring the project’s goals are clearly conveyed.

The leaflet is designed for a format of 8,5 x 5,5 cm and the brochure for an A4 format, trifold into 210 x 97 cm.

Figure 3: FIC-Fighters flyer.

Figure 4: FIC-Fighters trifold brochure.

Both resources are available via the project website: <https://fic-fighters.eu/media-kit/>

4 FIC-Fighters roll-up

The FIC-Fighters roll up banner (Figure 5) has been designed to introduce key information about the project in a visually appealing way. The banner can be used by partners at different types of events where FIC-Fighters will be promoted. It can be used both at events targeting the general public or other stakeholder groups such as policy makers, industry or scientific audiences.

The roll-up banner is designed for a standard size of 80 x 200 cm.

Figure 5: FIC-Fighters roll-up.

The banner is available via the project website: <https://fic-fighters.eu/media-kit/>

5 FIC-Fighters poster

The FIC-Fighters poster template (Figure 6) offers a similar content structure as the trifold brochure. This template, provided in PowerPoint format, is accessible to all partners, ensuring flexibility and ease of customisation. Partners can modify the content to tailor it for specific purposes and adapt it to align with the focus of the event where FIC-Fighters is being presented.

Figure 6: FIC-Fighters poster template.

The poster template is available to partners via the internal repository. It is designed for an A1 format.

6 FIC-Fighters video

The animated video is a key communication tool for promoting the FIC-Fighters project. This initiative aims to effectively communicate the project's objectives, impact, and importance to a broad audience.

The introductory video is a tool to showcase the project's purpose, and societal and environmental importance in an accessible and engaging manner. The goal is to inform all stakeholders on how the project contributes to EU strategic priorities, such as sustainability and industry competitiveness. The video also aims to inspire potential collaborators, policymakers, or citizens to take an interest in the project, support its outcomes, and get involved.

Target audiences:

- **General public:** This is the main target audience. Citizens within the EU may benefit from the project outcomes or wish to understand how EU funds are being utilised for societal good.

- **Other stakeholders:** Policy-makers, industry leaders, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and academic institutions who may collaborate or benefit from the project's findings.

Presenting what could be considered complex information in a visually engaging and easy-to-understand format, the animated video acts as a bridge between the project and its diverse audience. Its ultimate aim is to enhance visibility, promote the positive impact of EU funding, and foster wider public and stakeholder support for the project.

Figure 7: Screenshot from the FIC-Fighters video.

The animated video was produced in close collaboration with all partners who reviewed and provided feedback on the different stages of the video production.

The video is available on the project website (<https://fic-fighters.eu/media-kit/>) and YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@FIC-Fighters>), and it will be promoted through all social media channels.

7 FIC-Fighters general presentation

The FIC-Fighters presentation (Figure 8) provides a set of slides introducing key information about the project. It offers a good basis for any project partner wishing to deliver a general introductory presentation. The slides can easily be expanded to include more details on specific aspects, as convenient.

Figure 8: Examples from the FIC-Fighters introductory presentation.

The presentation template is available to partners via the internal repository.

8 FIC-Fighters templates

Different templates have been made available to Consortium partners via the project’s internal repository. The project stylebook (see Annex 1 of Deliverable 6.1) specifies the formatting rules for each of these.

Currently the following templates are available:

- Powerpoint template
- Deliverable template
- Presentation template
- Poster template

9 FIC-Fighters media-kit

The media kit for journalists, policymakers or anybody else interested in FIC-Fighters has been carefully compiled to convey the key messages of the FIC-Fighters project, highlighting the potential of converting phosphogypsum into valuable new products using sustainable and zero-waste processes. The kit aims to raise awareness and foster understanding of the project’s objectives, innovative methodologies, and anticipated outcomes among its target audiences.

The media kit includes the project logo files, a slide deck, the project video, the flyer and brochure as well as the roll-up banner. The kit will be further complete with other materials such as factsheets.

The media kit is publicly available via the project website: <https://fic-fighters.eu/media-kit/>

Press Releases		Media Kit
Asset Type	Description	Download Link
Logo	High-resolution project logo in various formats (PNG, SVG)	Download ZIP
Presentation	Slide deck with project highlights and goals	Download PPT
Flyer	A business-card sized flyer for distribution at events	Download flyer
Brochure	A trifold brochure providing detailed information	Download brochure
Roll-up	A roll-up banner for events	Download roll-up

Figure 9: Screenshot from the FIC-Fighters media kit webpage.

The media kit will play an important role in supporting upcoming press releases distributed to media outlets. It will also serve as a valuable resource for project partners attending events, enabling them to easily access and share information about the project’s vision, goals, and achievements. By combining visual, written, and digital components, the media kit aims to maximise outreach and impact.